

MEDICAL SCIENCES

USE OF A BEAM FIXATION SYSTEM IN THE MANUFACTURE OF PARTIALLY REMOVABLE DENTURES

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Abstract

Treatment of patients with secondary partial adentia is still relevant today, since the prevalence of this pathology remains high. The need for orthopedic treatment with removable dentures, according to various authors, ranges from 30 to 60%. However, not all patients use removable dentures made for them. The reasons may be: a poorly made prosthesis, a problem with fixation, the psychological mood of the patient, and more.

Keywords: partial edentia, removable dentures, beam fixation.

Today, removable dentures with support and fixation on a beam are used to optimally solve the problems of fixing and stabilizing a denture and distributing the chewing load on abutment teeth or implants. Such fastening of removable dentures, combined with a high therapeutic and aesthetic effect, allows one to achieve good results in treatment. However, there are still unresolved issues related to beam structures. At the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry of the Belarusian State Medical University, we conducted a number of experiments in order to study this problem.

The purpose of the study is to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment of patients with a small number of remaining teeth by substantiating various options for the location of the beam and fixation of removable dentures.

Material and methods.

The object of study is the lower jaw of a cadaveric human skull. The studies were carried out using holographic interferometry. In our experiments, we used a helium, neon laser with a wavelength of $\lambda=632$ Nm [1.3.5.]. When studying the results of the study and further prosthetics with beam structures, we believe that with a small number of remaining teeth and their linear arrangement, beams are indicated, the matrix of which can make certain movements on it (semi-labile connection) or if there is a gap between the beam and the matrix. This is due to the fact that when the prosthesis is rigidly fixed to the supporting teeth, there is a large dislocation moment. This is especially true when the beam is linearly located and there is no distal support. If there are teeth from different functionally oriented groups and the beam is located along the plane, the fixation can be more rigid. In the presence of mobile teeth of the first degree, you can use a beam fastening for overlapping dentures, fixing the beam on the roots. Various types of beams and fixing elements were used to treat

patients. Results. Based on the experiments conducted and long-term results of treatment, we recommend: in order to reduce the rate of atrophy of the prosthetic bed, all patients with a small number of remaining teeth should have individual trays made to obtain functional impressions under arbitrary pressure or in cases of pronounced compliance of the mucous membrane of compression impressions. Artificial teeth must be placed in articulators. After applying the prostheses, check their fit to the prosthetic bed and identify areas of high pressure using low-viscosity silicone materials. In cases of loose fit of the prosthesis base due to technological errors, carry out laboratory relining of the prostheses. The presence of premature contacts must be identified and carefully eliminated by grinding [2.4]. When providing prosthetics to patients with a small number of remaining teeth, given the complexity of the clinical problems that arise, clinical observation is necessary, regardless of the method of fixation of removable dentures. The frequency of examinations should be at least once every 6-12 months. An even more significant reduction in individual intervals between visits is recommended in case of unfavorable course of periodontal diseases, low effectiveness of periodontal treatment or refusal of it, endocrine diseases, poor oral hygiene and different types of prostheses. When balancing of the prosthesis base appears, it is necessary to carry out laboratory relining.

Conclusion.

Regular replacement of elastic elements (matrices) and labile clamps of locking fastenings helps prevent abrasion and deformation of the metal parts of the locking fastening (matrix, support-stabilizing lining, milled surface of the crown, matrix bed), and reduces the side effects of the prosthesis on the prosthetic bed. Timely activation of precision activated clasps improves the fixation and functional properties of removable dentures.

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